

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-298-ADH-1% 05	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	103	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 298
Injection Volume:	30.00 ul	Channel Name:	272.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 272.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/1/2023 9:48:46 AM CST		
Date Processed:	5/23/2023 9:04:19 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	17.076	222241	27.39	12166
2	17.924	187283	23.09	9431
3	21.333	178706	22.03	6985
4	22.463	223041	27.49	7872

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-299-ADH-1% 05	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	103	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400 05
Injection #:	3	Processing Method:	LRM 4 299
Injection Volume:	20.00 ul	Channel Name:	272.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 272.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/1/2023 11:16:33 AM CST		
Date Processed:	5/23/2023 9:09:21 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	16.877	1129	0.06	124
2	17.694	36056	1.99	1788
3	21.247	2038	0.11	153
4	22.369	1769227	97.83	60514